

Temple of Ninurta at Nimrud (ancient Kalhu)

By Glynnis Maynard, University of Cambridge

Entry tags: Archaeological Site, Religious Group, Assyrian Religions, Near East, Polytheistic, Religious Place, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Religious Complex

The temple of Ninurta is located on the citadel of the Neo-Assyrian city of Kalhu (also known as Nimrud). Kalhu was an imperial capital from 883-706 BCE but had a longer history as an Assyrian city from around 1350 to 610 BCE. The temple was part of a wider architectural landscape of temple complexes and palaces on the citadel, first begun by Ashurnasirpal II (r. 883-859) but sustained and renovated by subsequent Neo-Assyrian kings and local governors. Located at the northern end of the citadel, the temple was immediately north of Ashurnasirpal II's new palace, southwest of the Ishtar-Sharrat-Niphi temple, and southeast of a ziggurat, which was also dedicated to Ninurta. Although Ashurnasirpal II explicitly states in inscriptions on the temple walls that the structure is a temple to Ninurta, the composite nature of Assyrian deities at the time may have meant that Ninurta shared visual aspects with the Assyrian gods Enlil and Ashur. By the Neo-Assyrian period, Ninurta was a god of war and agriculture. This variability could have been reflected in elements of temple decoration, relief iconography, and cult statues located therein. Archaeological finds from Nimrud are located in museums in Baghdad and Mosul, as well as in at least 74 other museums worldwide. Many archaeological projects have excavated in this area of Kalhu, but the temple itself has not been fully excavated and published architectural plans do not agree upon the relationship of the temple to surrounding structures. Until recently, Ashurnasirpal II's palace and main temples on the citadel, including the area of the Ninurta temple and ziggurat, were maintained as an archaeological park to encourage tourism and public engagement with the site. However, in 2015 Daesh destroyed the vast majority of unearthed structures on the citadel. Restoration projects are currently underway to recover the site.

Date Range: 865 BCE - 612 BCE

Region: Nimrud

Region tags: Middle East, Northern Iraq, Iraq

The ancient site of Kalhu (modern Nimrud) is situated 35 kilometers south of the modern city of Mosul in Northern Iraq. The city itself covers an area of approximately 890 acres, or 3.5 sq km.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Water source

Notes: located on (then) eastern bank of Tigris river

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: raised citadel located in SW quadrant of city

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The temple has not been completely excavated. The latest excavations conducted by Mallowan delineated a series of rooms to the west of a paved area that was probably a courtyard. The most recent hypothesis by Reade (2002) posits that the 'Ninurta temple' might be part of a wider complex that includes other temples in the Northwest corner of the citadel, including shrines to multiple gods within the total structure.

↳ A group of structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: see above note under 'a single structure'

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Temple construction was begun by Ashurnasirpal II (r. 883-859 BCE) and completed by his son Shalmaneser III (r. 859-824 BCE).

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: see above note on 'a single structure'

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: communal and individual

Notes: Room 3 (according to Mallowan's architectural plans and excavation notes) had two rows of large storage jars, which may have originally held oil for use in temple activities.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– I don't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

Notes: Nimrud was attacked in 614 and 612 BCE.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Inscriptions on series of inner walls of the excavated structure specify its dedication to Ninurta.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that shrines dedicated to other gods or goddesses may have been present in the larger temple complex, particularly Enlil and/or Adad.

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Oates, J. and Oates, D. 2001. Nimrud: An Assyrian Imperial City Revealed. London: British School of Archaeology in Iraq.
- Source 2: Mallowan, M.E.L. 1966. Nimrud and its remains. London: Collins.
- Source 3: Reade, J.E. 2002. The Ziggurat and Temples of Nimrud. Iraq 64: 135-216

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL:
<http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/nimrud/ancientkalhu/thecity/zigguratandtemples/index.html>
- Source 1 Description: Ziggurat and temples webpage of the 'Materialities of Assyrian Knowledge Production: Object Biographies of Inscribed Artefacts from Nimrud' project

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

Notes: Nimrud was excavated in the 19th century by Henry Austen Layard (1845-1847, 1849-1851), Henry Rawlinson (1852), Hormudz Rassam (1853-4, 1878-1880), William Loftus (1854-55), George Smith (1873)

– Yes

|

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Modern excavations at Nimrud were conducted by: the British School of Archaeology in Iraq: Max E.L. Mallowan (1949-1957), David Oates (1958-1962), and Julian Orchard (1963); the Directorate of Antiquities of the Republic of Iraq, including Muyasser Sa'id and Muzahim Mahmud (1956, 1959-60, 1969-1978, 1982-1992, 2000); the Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology at the University of Warsaw: Janusz Meusyński (1974-1976); the Centro Ricerche Archeologiche e Scavi di Torino: Paolo Fiorina (1987-1989); the British Museum: John Curtis and Dominique Collon (1989)

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Notes: from roughly 2014-2016, Daesh/Islamic State looted and destroyed vast areas of the Nimrud citadel

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: The exact relationship between the Ninurta temple complex and surrounding temples, ziggurat and palace is still unclear, but all four of the aforementioned structures in this northwestern quadrant of the citadel probably interacted with each other in various ways. However, the citadel itself was bounded from the rest of the city by a mud-brick wall at least 15 meters high in some places.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The temple complex is located on the citadel with other important temples and palaces.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

- King or emperor

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

- Yes

↳ Groups:

- Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: In royal inscriptions, Assyrian kings often describe temple building in the first-person without naming specific groups of people. However, we know that the carving of images upon wall panels lining temples and palaces required specialized craftspeople. It is also possible that building the actual structure required the labor of slaves, corvee labourers, and/or captured enemies.

- Corvee labourers
- Men

Notes: Letter K 382 mentions the dedication of a man to the Ninurta temple as corvée labor (Kataja and Whiting 1995: 116).

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

- No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

- No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

- No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

- No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Other [specify]: Temple building (and restoration) was considered an important task for Assyrian kings to consistently fulfill.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

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Type of excavation:

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Notes: from roughly 2014-2016, Daesh/Islamic State looted and destroyed vast areas of the Nimrud citadel

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Water source

Notes: located on (then) eastern bank of Tigris river

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: raised citadel located in SW quadrant of city

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: The exact relationship between the Ninurta temple complex and surrounding temples, ziggurat and palace is still unclear, but all four of the aforementioned structures in this northwestern quadrant of the citadel probably interacted with each other in various ways. However, the citadel itself was bounded from the rest of the city by a mud-brick wall at least 15 meters high in some places.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The temple complex is located on the citadel with other important temples and palaces.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The temple has not been completely excavated. The latest excavations conducted by Mallowan delineated a series of rooms to the west of a paved area that was probably a courtyard. The most recent hypothesis by Reade (2002) posits that the 'Ninurta temple' might be part of a wider complex that includes other temples in the Northwest corner of the citadel, including shrines to multiple gods within the total structure.

A group of structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: see above note under 'a single structure'

A group of features:

– Yes

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Temple construction was begun by Ashurnasirpal II (r. 883-859 BCE) and completed by his son Shalmaneser III (r. 859-824 BCE).

Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

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Notes: see above note on 'a single structure'

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

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– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: communal and individual

Notes: Room 3 (according to Mallowan's architectural plans and excavation notes) had two rows of large storage jars, which may have originally held oil for use in temple activities.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

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↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– I don't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

Notes: Nimrud was attacked in 614 and 612 BCE.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Inscriptions on series of inner walls of the excavated structure specify its dedication to Ninurta.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that shrines dedicated to other gods or goddesses may have been present in the larger temple complex, particularly Enlil and/or Adad.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: In royal inscriptions, Assyrian kings often describe temple building in the first-person without naming specific groups of people. However, we know that the carving of images upon wall panels lining temples and palaces required specialized craftspeople. It is also possible that building the actual structure required the labor of slaves, corvee labourers, and/or captured enemies.

– Corvee labourers

– Men

Notes: Letter K 382 mentions the dedication of a man to the Ninurta temple as corvée labor

(Kataja and Whiting 1995: 116).

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Temple building (and restoration) was considered an important task for Assyrian kings to consistently fulfill.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: limited evidence of glazed brick on exterior walls

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The doorway of an east-facing façade looking into a courtyard was flanked by multiple sculpted guardian figures: two human-headed winged lions as well as three

winged figures adjacent to each lion (room a/4). Internal walls were covered in sculpted mythological scenes, royal inscriptions, and wall paintings.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Ninurta

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: winged and unwinged protective figures; figures wearing a fish cloak (apkallu); bird-headed and winged figures (apkallu); Anzû, a monster with the head, forelegs and body of a lion and the wings, hind leg talons, and feathered tail of a bird

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: human-headed winged lions; bird and fish apkallu

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: chevron decoration

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: palmette and vegetal

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Inscription on some of the interior and gateway relief panels over top of the carved images

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: There are no statues present today, but there would have been when the temple was in use. Although the original statue of Ninurta housed in the temple does not survive, one of Ashurnasirpal II's inscriptions describe the god's image as 'made out of fine mountain stone and red gold' (ANP.1, ii.133).

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on either side of the doorway leading into room c is thought to illustrate

Ninurta (the dedicated god) battling with the monster Anzû. See British Museum object 124571: https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/W_1851-0902-501

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: Some reliefs depict protective guardian spirits

Notes: A stele of Ashurnasirpal II was found outside the doorway of temple room c. According to its inscription, it was originally meant to be displayed in a royal palace, and so may have been moved here by a later Assyrian king. See British Museum object: 118805 https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/W_1851-0902-32

↳ Are there paintings present:
– Yes

Notes: During his excavations, Layard mentioned that the walls inside room 4 were painted with multicolored figures and ornamental designs (1853: 352).

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:
– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:
– Yes

↳ Type
–Other [specify]: unclear if they were painting on dry or wet plaster

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions on wall panels would begin with a dedication to Ninurta, then could proceed with a list of royal titles, historical narratives of military conquest and/or restoration of temples, and finish with a series of prayers and/or blessings for future kings, and sometimes curse formulae against defacement of inscription.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: glazed brick in interior of structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's not clear if the temple was connected to the adjacent ziggurat. It is also not clear if the temple to Ninurta was part of a larger temple complex housing other gods and goddesses.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: A variety of guardian anthropomorphic figures helped protect and bless the temple, including apkallu and lamassu.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Only surviving depiction of what is argued to be Ninurta battling Anzû at the entrance of room c. This depiction, if identified correctly, would be based off of the Anzû myth.

↳ Human narratives

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The ziggurat at the Northwestern corner of the citadel was also dedicated to Ninurta and was immediately adjacent to the temple, and there may have been direct access to the ziggurat via the temple. However, we do not know the exact dimensions (including shape and height) of the ziggurat. Recently, 60m x 60m has been proposed.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

Notes: A height of around 10 m for the walls of the temple is the most recent postulation, by Reade (2002: 165).

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Notes: An inscription on a lion (ANP.28) at the entrance to the neighboring Ishtar-Sharrat-Niphi temple claims that the buildings housing various gods and goddesses in Nimrud had cedar roofs and cedar doors. Parts of cedar wood beams were found in multiple rooms in the temple. Cedar was imported from the Northern Levant and was highly prized in Mesopotamian palace and temple building.

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The interior and exterior wall panels were made of gypsum, which is calcium

sulfate. Also stone thresholds, paving stones, dais.

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mud-brick and worked stone

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
 - No

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: It's not clear if the temple was connected to the adjacent ziggurat. It is also not clear if the temple to Ninurta was part of a larger temple complex housing other gods and goddesses.

- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
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– Yes

- ↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
 - Field doesn't know

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:
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Notes: The interior and exterior wall panels were made of gypsum, which is calcium sulfate. Also stone thresholds, paving stones, dais.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mud-brick and worked stone

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: limited evidence of glazed brick on exterior walls

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The doorway of an east-facing façade looking into a courtyard was flanked by multiple sculpted guardian figures: two human-headed winged lions as well as three winged figures adjacent to each lion (room a/4). Internal walls were covered in sculpted mythological scenes, royal inscriptions, and wall paintings.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

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↳ Is the decoration figural:

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– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Ninurta

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: winged and unwinged protective figures; figures wearing a fish cloak (apkallu); bird-headed and winged figures (apkallu); Anzû, a monster with the head, forelegs and body of a lion and the wings, hind leg talons, and feathered tail of a bird

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: human-headed winged lions; bird and fish apkallu

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: chevron decoration

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: palmette and vegetal

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Inscription on some of the interior and gateway relief panels over top of the carved images

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: There are no statues present today, but there would have been when the temple was in use. Although the original statue of Ninurta housed in the temple does not survive, one of

Ashurnasirpal II's inscriptions describe the god's image as 'made out of fine mountain stone and red gold' (ANP.1, ii.133).

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:
– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on either side of the doorway leading into room c is thought to illustrate Ninurta (the dedicated god) battling with the monster Anzû. See British Museum object 124571: https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/W_1851-0902-501

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: Some reliefs depict protective guardian spirits

Notes: A stele of Ashurnasirpal II was found outside the doorway of temple room c. According to its inscription, it was originally meant to be displayed in a royal palace, and so may have been moved here by a later Assyrian king. See British Museum object: 118805 https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/W_1851-0902-32

↳ Are there paintings present:
– Yes

Notes: During his excavations, Layard mentioned that the walls inside room 4 were painted with multicolored figures and ornamental designs (1853: 352).

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– Other [specify]: unclear if they were painting on dry or wet plaster

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions on wall panels would begin with a dedication to Ninurta, then could proceed with a list of royal titles, historical narratives of military conquest and/or restoration of temples, and finish with a series of prayers and/or blessings for future kings, and sometimes curse formulae against defacement of inscription.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Yes [specify]: glazed brick in interior of structure

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes

Notes: A variety of guardian anthropomorphic figures helped protect and bless the temple, including apkallu and lamassu.

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No

- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No

- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No

- ↳ Humans
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes

Notes: Only surviving depiction of what is argued to be Ninurta battling Anzû at the entrance of room c. This depiction, if identified correctly, would be based off of the Anzû myth.

- ↳ Human narratives
 - Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Notes: The statues of various gods at Kalhu were apparently brought out from their shrines and moved about, which Reade (2002: 200) suggests could have taken place as part of a festival.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
– Yes

Notes: A deposit of cylinder seals and beads was found in a blocked corridor running N-S on the western side of the temple. Probably deposited in the 9th century BCE.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's unclear to what extent ancient Mesopotamians believed that supernatural creatures existed in the 'real' and could be 'seen.'

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Similarly to the query above, it is unclear if the apotropaic/beneficent roles attributed to supernatural beings in temples could be psychosomatically felt.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that the Ninurta temple space had to remain ritually clean but we do not have any texts to confirm this specific case.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: By the 7th century BCE, there were still priests who served Ninurta at Kalhu (Kataja and Whiting 1995: 116-122).

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: The cult statue of Ninurta (along with the other gods and goddesses within temples on the Kalhu

citadel) does not survive, but we know it was once there.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:
– Field doesn't know

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's unclear to what extent ancient Mesopotamians believed that supernatural creatures existed in the 'real' and could be 'seen.'

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

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Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

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Notes: The cult statue of Ninurta (along with the other gods and goddesses within temples on the Kalhu citadel) does not survive, but we know it was once there.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

- Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

- No

Are material offerings present:

- Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
 - Yes

Notes: A deposit of cylinder seals and beads was found in a blocked corridor running N-S on the western side of the temple. Probably deposited in the 9th century BCE.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

- Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

- Yes

- ↳ Is it required:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that the Ninurta temple space had to remain ritually clean but we do not

have any texts to confirm this specific case.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– Yes

Notes: By the 7th century BCE, there were still priests who served Ninurta at Kalhu (Kataja and Whiting 1995: 116-122).

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– I don't know

Notes: The statues of various gods at Kalhu were apparently brought out from their shrines and moved about, which Reade (2002: 200) suggests could have taken place as part of a festival.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: The temple had its own treasury and staff.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: votive dedications

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: One letter records a šangû-priest and chief singer, as well as a cook, steward, and doorkeeper

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - I don't know

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:
– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– Yes
Notes: controlled monetary resources

- ↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Does this place lease out land:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
 - I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the

group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: One letter records a šangû-priest and chief singer, as well as a cook, steward, and doorkeeper

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: The temple had its own treasury and staff.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: controlled monetary resources

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: votive dedications

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Temple of Ninurta at Nimrud (ancient Kalhu), Reade, J. E.. "The Ziggurat and Temples of Nimrud". *Iraq* 64 (2002): 135–216. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4200523>.

Reference: Temple of Ninurta at Nimrud (ancient Kalhu), Oates, J., and David Oates. *Nimrud: An Assyrian Imperial City Revealed*. London: British Institute for the Study of Iraq, 2001.

Reference: Temple of Ninurta at Nimrud (ancient Kalhu), Mallowan, M. E. L.. *Nimrud and Its Remains*. London: Collins, 1966.

Reference: Temple of Ninurta at Nimrud (ancient Kalhu), Kataja, L., and R. Whiting. *Grants, Decrees and Gifts of the Neo-assyrian Period (state Archives of Assyria 12)*. Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 2018.

Reference: Temple of Ninurta at Nimrud (ancient Kalhu), Postgate, J. N., and J. E. Reade. "Kalhu". *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie* 5 (1980): 303–23.

Reference: Temple of Ninurta at Nimrud (ancient Kalhu), Liverani, M.. *The Ancient Near East: History, Society, and Economy*. London: Routledge, 2013.

Reference: Temple of Ninurta at Nimrud (ancient Kalhu), Zamazalová, Silvie. "The Ziggurat and Its Temples". *Nimrud: Materialities of Assyrian Knowledge Production*, 2015. <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/nimrud/ancientkalhu/thecity/zigguratandtemples/index.html>.